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Effect of Personality Traits, Organization Culture and Work Incentives on Ethical Behavior at Work Place

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Abstract

This study is about the effect of personality traits, work place incentives and organization culture on ethical behavior at work place. The three independent variables are taken in this study to make it a comprehensive study. The measuring scales are adopted from the reliable sources. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of personality traits, work place incentives and organizational culture on ethical behavior of the employees. After the whole analysis it is found and conclude that, if personality traits and organization culture are good and favorable then there are greater chances that employees will behave ethically or positively. Where on the given sample information about the work place incentives it is analyzed that work place incentive do not positively affect the ethical behavior at work place. The work incentives do not have significant impact on ethical behavior of employees at work place.

Keywords: *Personality Traits, Organization Culture, Work Incentives, Ethical Behavior*

Introduction

Unethical behavior becomes a serious discussion in today's globalized world, where the organization are facing this issue and suffering. The factors that affect the ethical behavior of employees at work place need to find out and investigation of their effects is necessary, how these factors affect the ethical behavior and what are circumstances which encourage this unethical behavior at work place. The five big personality traits have greater influence on the ethical behavior in the organization. Furthermore the organization culture tends to increase the bad deeds in the organization (Dirk Holtbrügge, Anastasia Baron and Carina B. Friedmann 2014). A study is done on ethical issue from different perspective summaries that awareness, individuals and organizations factors and moral intensity have greater contribution in ethical decision making in the organization (Terry W. Loe, Linda Ferrell, Phylis Mansfield). For the success in the business and smooth working of operations of the organizations this is necessary to balance the behaviors of the employees at work place, for this purpose the organization should acknowledge and measure the contribution of organization culture and personality characteristics effecting the ethical behavior in the organization, and to control these factors the management should make favorable strategies (Hershcovis et al, 2007).

The incentives in our study are also taken to see the impact on ethical behavior at work place. By exploring the literature about the incentives plan a study by Harvard business review “Alfie kohn” found that the incentives plans do not change the attitude and behaviors of employees towards the organization. The incentive, bonuses, and other forms of compensations have not impact on the individual attitude and behaviors (Alfie kohn).

Objectives of Study

Followings are core objectives of this study:

- To investigate the impact of organization culture, personal traits and workplace incentives on the ethical behavior of the employees in the organizations.
- To check the relationship among the organization culture, personal traits and workplace incentives and ethical behavior at work place.
- To contribute the comprehensive study in the literature.

Theoretical Contribution

In this study three factors are taken collectively (personality traits, organization culture, and work place incentives) to analyze their effect on ethical behavior of employees at work place. This is a comprehensive study which will make it unique in the literature because many studies are done on ethics but these studies include onetime just only one factor to see the impact on ethical behavior. In this study three factors are collectively taken which will make this study more useful for future studies.

Practical Contribution

This research of investigation of the impact of organization culture, personal traits and workplace incentives on the ethical behavior of the employees in the organizations will help the management of the organizations and human resource managers as well, to know the causes of unethical behavior of employees during their work. The significance results of this study will encourage the management of the companies to take the steps and make strategies to control this behavior. However this study have numerous importance in itself, it will contribute and improve the literature.

Research Questions

Following are the research questions of this study:

- How personality traits, workplace incentives and organization culture effect ethical behavior at the work place?
- Is there positive effect or negative effect of personality traits, workplace incentives and organization culture on ethical behavior at the work place?

Delimitations of the Study

Followings are delimitations of this study:

- This research is not international or national level due to the lack of resources.
- We did not review the literature of 19th century; all the literature used in the research is after 2000 because this study is based on latest literature.
- We are not discussing or targeting the population related to the managerial level because the aim of study is to judge the ethical behavior at work and usually the managerial level of the organizations have ethical trainings, and there is need to know the ethical behaviors of the workers at work.
- We are just targeting the Service Industry located in Gujrat, because we are using the convenient sampling technique and from that industry we can easily and conveniently collect data from it.

Literature Review

Many studies are explored from the literature; many researchers conduct their studies from different perspectives and conclude different results. One of the study done by (Holtbrügge, Baron and Friedmann) in Germany on the big five personality attributes and their impact on ethical behavior, they found that personal traits have much influence on the ethical behavior of the employees. And there is significant relation of organization culture and misbehavior of the organizations employees (Holtbrügge, Baron and Friedmann 2014).

The manner which is used to apply business ethics sooner or later influences the economical performances of every. External environment different changes gives tough time even to the experienced firms that is why they tend to use immoral practices for the purpose of being part of the market or to maintain the level and reputation of the company. In spite of all these changes, for the purpose of maintaining the reputation and image of the company and for the purpose of being part of the competitive advantages on a long term the companies should be in a position to develop a strategic way of thinking that how they are following the business ethics. According to the levels of following the business ethics the companies are defined as the immoral firms which means profit oriented firms, legal firms which means firms that follows the principles of ethics. The management is the one which decides the type of organizational culture it supports in order for the company to be perceived as moral and socially responsible (MILITARU & Adriana, 2012).

Investigating and predicting the ethical decision making in the organization an inductively driven model is used by the Trevino in this research. The model describes that how the managers think about the ethical dilemmas. It also posits the relationship between the cognition and action based on other individual and situational variables. However with the adaptation of the moral judgment construct, future investigation can benefit from the measurement tools available. Future agenda should be developed for the future investigation of the ethical decision making in the organizations because it is the need of the proposed model and propositions add to the conceptual base. (Trevino, 1986).

There are three avenues of the research. The first is to assess whether individual ethical cultures are transformable by organizational ethical culture. The second part of the research reflects the study among the different kinds of the professionals that is IT professionals, nurses etc. And the third type is about the political nature of the organizational culture. This article specifically talks about the empirical; relationship between the company's code of ethics and the ethical behavior at work and this article also describes the importance and effectiveness of the ethical codes on the behavior of the employees and also add to the employee's ethical awareness, training, and the enforcements of the codes of ethics. With the passage of time the ethical culture is becoming more important element of the organizational overall culture. The authors of this manuscript would like go one step further and, based on personal experiences, state that it pays mentally, physically, spiritually, and economically to be ethical. (Ampofo & Mujtaba, 2011).

The companies are facing different types of problems due to the ethical issues in the recent years and there is no doubt that they will also face these problems in the future. very good and well defined ethical practices are not very easy to maintain but with the help of the well-designed policies of the ethical issues we can apply the good ethical practices into the management, processes and the strategies of the companies all these steps will help to move the organization to the good ethical culture. Conclusively the article describes that the companies should have to develop a defined organizational culture and they also have to be in a position to manage the ethical problems if they occur the business operations. In spite of all the challenges and problems companies should have to maintain the ethical culture in the organization because it is very helpful in motivating the inner and also the outsider customers and employees of the companies. As a consequence, this may not only reduce the unhealthy environment that began the financial crisis, but will also help in restoring the health of the financial system that caused it. (GRAHAM, 2012)

A Meta-analytic Review of Research Studies” A recent article by (Leyten and Kurvers and Preller et al) are the strong supports for the claims that incentives at work place can considerably increase work performance when they are carefully implemented and performance is measured before and during incentive programs and also include that the financial benefit of increasing performance 22% in m most organizations. When specific Features of incentive programs were analyzed; it was clear that some programs produced significantly more than 22%. The most remarkable example is the 48% increase in team performance.

The Netherlands Organization for Applied Scientific Research is suggesting that improving the working environment and work place incentives results in a decrease in the number of complaints and absenteeism and an increase in efficiency (Bluysen et al). The ethical climate of an organization is linked straight to the positive behaviors of employees and also to a range of negative work behaviors as well as delay, absenteeism, and social loafing (Peterson, 2002).

Recent research has paying attention on the role ethics plays in the scope of organizational climate and employee behavior. This includes the effect leaders or administrators have on their employee’s behavior as well. The most popular reasons behind the occurrence of deviant workplace behaviors is the conflicting perception, via deviant role models, that the organization supports such behavior (Appelbaum, Iaconi, &Matousek, 2007).

Negative work behaviors also are linked to decreases in job satisfaction and organizational commitment, lower levels of creativity, stagnated productivity, increased antisocial behavior, as well as increased employee turnover (Appelbaum et al., 2007; Morrison, 2008; Peterson, 2002).

Methodology

Research Type

This research is primary type of research and the data is collected from the workers of the service industry Gujrat.

Data Collection Tool

This is a primary research therefore the data is collected from the employees (workers/machine operators) through questionnaire.

Time Frame

The time frame which we have used in this research is not large; we have just collected data from the workers of the company in the year 2015.

Sample

The targeted population of our research is Service industry located in the Gujrat city and our research is based on the workers (machine operators) of the company and the sample size of the study is 406 workers of the company while the total population of the company (located in the Gujrat) is 4000. The 406 numbers of observations are taken into consideration in this research and the sample size is calculated by the “Taro Yamani’ formula.

$$n = N / 1 + N (e)^2$$

Margin of Error

The margin of error is 0.05 in this research.

Sampling Technique

In this research we used the convenient sampling technique and the data is collected from the, conveniently available workers of the Service industry (Gujrat).

Scale

To measure the relationship of all variable different scales are adopted as measuring tool. To measure the personality trait the scale of (The big five questionnaire, A new questionnaire to access the five factor model) is adopted. Further to measure the organization culture the measuring scales is adopted from (Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire, D Talcott). The measurement scale of work incentives is adopted from (Perceptions of Incentives in Business and Government, G Rainey). The scale of independent variable is taken from (The Corporate Ethical Virtues Model, Muel Kaptein).

Likert Scale

Likert scale is (1) for strongly agree (2) for agree (3) for neutral (4) for strongly disagree (5) for disagree.

Theoretical Framework

Hypothesis Development

H1: There is negative relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior at work.

H2: There is positive relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior at work.

H3: There is negative relationship between work place incentives and ethical behavior at work.

H4: There is positive relationship between work place incentives and ethical behavior at work.

H5: There is negative relationship between organizational culture and ethical behavior at work.

H6: There is positive relationship between organization culture and ethical behavior at work

Analysis and Results

Descriptive Statistics

	Gender	Age	Personality_Traits	Work_Incentives	Organizational_Culture	Ethical_Behavior
N	Valid	406	406	406	406	406
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.4680	23.2488	15.3153	11.8842	14.0936
Median		1.0000	23.0000	15.0000	11.0000	14.0000
Std. Deviation		.50938	4.09513	3.58586	3.96514	3.36373
Minimum		1.00	11.00	7.00	5.00	7.00
Maximum		3.00	39.00	27.00	59.00	31.00

Interpretation

On the bases of results and tables are showing total responded are 406, and there is no missing value. Means of age is 1.4680, PT 23.24, WI 15.31, OC 11, 8842 and EB is 14.09. The median of age is 1.48, PT 23.00, WI 15.00, OC is 11.00 and RB is 14.00. Std. Deviation of age is .50, PT is 4.0, WI is 3.5 OC 3.9 and at the end EB Std.D is 3.3.

Minimum value of age is 1.00 and maximum is 3.0, PT mini 11 and maxi 39, WI Mini 7.00 and maxi 27.00, OC mini 5.00 and maxi 59.00, and EB minimum is 7.00 and maximum is 31.00.

Frequencies

Followings are the Frequency results of Gender.

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	197	48.5	48.5	48.5
Valid Female	209	51.5	51.5	100.0
Total	406	100.0	100.0	

Followings are Frequency results of Age.

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 20 to 24	218	53.7	53.7	53.7
Valid 25 to 29	186	45.8	45.8	99.5
Valid 30 to 35	2	.5	.5	100.0
Total	406	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation of Frequency

On the bases of results, Total responded are 406 males are 197 (48.5%) and females are 209 (51.5%). In Age 20 to 24 are 218 respondent and 25 to 29 are 186, 30 to 35 are only 2 respondent.

Correlation Analysis

Correlations

		Personality_Traits	Work_Incentives	Organizational_Culture	Ethical_Behavior
Personality_Traits	Pearson Correlation	1	.380**	.395**	.289**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	406	406	406	406
Work_Incentives	Pearson Correlation	.380**	1	.398**	.320**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	406	406	406	406
Organizational_Culture	Pearson Correlation	.395**	.398**	1	.234**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	406	406	406	406
Ethical_Behavior	Pearson Correlation	.289**	.320**	.234**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	406	406	406	406

Interpretation

The above mentioned table describes that there is relationship between the personality traits and the work incentives and the relationship between them is significant as cleared from the p-value (0.000) which is less than the alpha which shows the significant relationship between the two, and the organizational culture and personality traits also have significant relationship between them and the work incentives also have significant relationship with the personality traits and the organizational culture. While the overall picture of the above table describes that all the variables shown in the above mentioned table, have significant relationship with each other.

Personality Traits and Ethical Behavior Analysis

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.823E2 ^a	475	.001
Likelihood Ratio	377.355	475	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	33.879	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	406		

In the above table the relationship of personality traits and ethical behavior is shown in the chi square value. The value of chi square is showing what is the relationship exist between the personality traits and ethical behavior at work place. From the chi square test analysis the chi square value is derived which is (0.001) this is less than the value of alpha (0.05). therefore on the basis of given p- value of chi square we reject the hypothesis H1 . Our H1 is that “there is negative relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior at work place” so H2 is accepted “ there is positive relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior” so we conclude that when the personality attributes are positive of employees there is greater chance of positive behavior of employees at work place. When the personality of employees has negative characteristics then the employees behave unethically.

Work Incentives and Ethical Behavior Analysis

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.045E2 ^a	361	.057
Likelihood Ratio	329.202	361	.884
Linear-by-Linear Association	41.568	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	406		

The p value of chi square test of work incentives and ethical behavior is (0.057) which is greater than alpha (0.05) therefore we accept the Hypothesis H4 which is that “there is negative relationship between work incentives and ethical behavior” so we conclude that there is negative relationship between work incentives and ethical behavior of employees at work place. It is not necessary when the work incentives are low employees behave unethically. From the given sample information it is prove that the low work incentives don't tends to increase unethical behavior of employees.

Organizational Culture and Ethical Behavior Analysis

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.020E2 ^a	361	.000
Likelihood Ratio	340.333	361	.776
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.085	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	406		

In the above table the p value of chi square is (0.000) which is significant and less than alpha (0.05). On the basis of p value we reject our hypothesis H5 “there is negative relationship between organization culture and ethical behavior” and we accept our Hypothesis H6 “there is positive relationship between organizational culture and ethical behavior”. So we conclude that there is positive relationship between organization culture and ethical behavior. When the organization culture is good and favorable then employees behave positively and ethically.

Limitations of Study

Followings are limitations of this study:

- This study just measures the ethical behavior of the employees of the service industry due to lack of resources.
- The findings of our research can be generalized to the population of service industry.
- The respondents in our research are the workers of the Service Industries and the responses are based on their knowledge and mentality.
- The instruments which we are using are the questioners in hard form which will be filled by the targeted population.
- The sample sized used in the research is restricted to 406 because our study just limited to service industry. .

Conclusion

From the whole analysis and after the results we come to now that there is significant relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior at work, work incentives and ethical behavior and organizational culture and ethical behavior at work. On the basis of the results we conclude that there is significant positive relationship between personality traits and ethical behavior at work. When there is good personality trait of the employees there are greater chances that he or she behaves ethically or in positive way at work place. The organizational culture and ethical behavior at work also have significant positive relationship. When the organizational conditions and culture is good the employees behave ethically and when the organization culture is not good the employees may behave unethically. From further analysis we found that there is insignificant relationship between work place incentive and ethical behavior. When the work incentives are low and high it is not necessary that employees behave in positive or negative way, so that ethical behavior is free from work incentives. So in few words we say that the two aspects (i) personality (ii) organizations culture have greater contribution in formation of behaviors where the work place incentive have little bit contribution.

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